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MAKTABGACHA
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- 13.00.00 Pedagogika fanlari
- 13.00.01 Pedagogika nazariyasi. Pedagogik ta'limotlar tarixi
- 13.00.02 Ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi (sohalar bo'yicha)
- 13.00.03 Maxsus pedagogika
- 13.00.04 Jismoniy tarbiya va sport mashg'ulotlari nazariyasi va metodikasi
- 13.00.05 Kasb-hunar ta'limi nazariyasi va metodikasi
- 13.00.06 Elektron ta'lim nazariyasi va metodikasi (ta'lim sohaları va bosqichlari bo'yicha)
- 13.00.07 Ta'limda menejment
- 13.00.08 Maktabgacha ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi
- 13.00.09 Ijtimoiy pedagogika
- 07.00.00 Tarix fanlari
- 19.00.00 Psixologiya fanlari
- 01.00.00 Fizika-matematika fanlari
- 02.00.00 Kimyo fanlari
- 03.00.00 Biologiya fanlari
- 09.00.00 Falsafa fanlari
- 10.00.00 Filologiya fanlari
- 11.00.00 Geografiya fanlari

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MUNDARIJA

Oilaning maktabgacha yoshdagi bolalar estetik tarbiyasidagi o'rni	24
<i>Abdullayeva Ma'sudaxon Abdubannayevna</i>	
Bo'lajak informatika o'qituvchilarini pedagogik faoliyatga metodik tayyorlash texnologiyalari	27
<i>Abdubannoyeva Muxlisaxon Iqboljon qizi, Abdullayev Alibek Qodiraliyevich</i>	
Oliy ta'lim muassasalarida bulutli xizmatlardan foydalanish zaruriyati	30
<i>Abdullayev Alibek Qodiraliyevich, Turdaliyeva Muslimaxon Jahongir qizi</i>	
Raqamli texnologiyalar yordamida fortepiano chalishni o'rgatish metodikasi	34
<i>Abduvaxobova Nilufar Abdumannon qizi</i>	
Maktabda fizika fanini o'qitishda innovatsion yondashuv	38
<i>Alinazarova Mahfuza</i>	
Tasavvufdagi "komil inson" konsepsiyasining hozirgi ta'lim tizimida shaxsga yo'naltirilgan yondashuv sifatida talqini	43
<i>Aqilxonov Saidolimxon Abdurashid o'g'li</i>	
Tabiiy-ilmiy savodxonlikni shakllantirish omillari va pedagogik shart-sharoitlar	48
<i>Choriyeva Gulbaxor Shotemirovna</i>	
Robototexnika fanini o'qitishda axborot texnologiyalaridan foydalanib mustaqil ta'limni tashkil etish	53
<i>Elmonov Sirojiddin Mamadiyarovich</i>	
Xalqaro baholash dasturlarida boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilarining o'qish savodxonligini baholash bo'yicha jahon tajribasi	58
<i>Ergasheva S. T.</i>	
Boshlang'ich ta'limda tabiiy fanlar orqali o'quvchilarning kognitiv salohiyatini rivojlantirish	61
<i>Eshmamatova Dilnoza Jovli qizi</i>	
Maktabgacha yoshdagi bolalarning aqliy salohiyatini oshirishda tarbiyachi mahorati	64
<i>Karimova Gulzodaxon Marufjon qizi</i>	
Bo'lajak texnologik ta'lim o'qituvchilarining kasbiy kompetensiyalarini rivojlantirishni takomillashtirish	68
<i>Hojikarimova Gulasal Tadjaliyevna</i>	
Xorijiy talabalarga o'zbek tilini o'rgatishda elektron platformalar yaratish	71
<i>Jo'rayeva Matluba</i>	
Bo'lajak o'qituvchilar uchun raqamli ta'lim muhitini modellashtirish va uning samaradorlik omillari	74
<i>Komilova Z. X.</i>	
O'qituvchi kasbiy faoliyatida muloqot madaniyati	80
<i>M. Yu. Mahkamova</i>	
Psixologiya fanini o'qitishda zamonaviy pedagogik texnologiyalar va talabalarda tahliliy fikrlashni shakllantirish masalalari	86
<i>Madazizova Dilfuza Raxmatullayevna</i>	
Integrating Listening and Speaking Skills in ESP (English for Specific Purposes) Classes	90
<i>Madina Tilavova</i>	
Bolalarni maktabga tayyorlash jarayonida neyropedagogik yondashuvlar	94
<i>N. O. Saidova</i>	
Tibbiyot oliy ta'lim muassasalarida radiologiya fanini o'qitishda raqamli texnologiyalarning metodologik roli	99
<i>Nazarova Gulchexra Shuxratdjonovna</i>	
Ijodkorlik tushunchasining mohiyati va uning ta'limdagi roli	103
<i>Ochilova Dilbar Isroilovna</i>	
Alaliyani boshqa nutqiy nuqsonlar bilan farqli xarakteristikasi	108
<i>Oripova Zilola</i>	
Ingliz tilini o'qitishda suggestopediya metodini joriy etishning samaradorligi	113
<i>Pulatova Sitora Abdurazzoq qizi</i>	
Oliy ta'lim muassasalari menejerlarining kasbiy-boshqaruv kompetentligi tushunchasi va uning tarkibiy qismlari	118
<i>Qarshiboyev Sharof Egamnazarovich</i>	
Koordinatsion qobiliyatlarni rivojlantirishning yosh badmintonchilar texnik-taktik tayyorgarligiga ta'siri	122
<i>Qurbanova Ilmira Alisher qizi</i>	

Blended Learning	125
Quvandikova Xadicha	
Fizika darslarida zamonaviy axborot texnologiyalaridan foydalanish	129
Raxmanov Valijon Turdaliyevich, O'razaliyev Alijon Xasan o'g'li	
“Qurilish jarayonlari texnologiyasi” fanida loyihalash kompetentligining tarkibiy tuzilmasi va uni raqamli ta'limga moslashtirish	135
Raxmonova Nazokat Umaraliyevna	
Vitagen texnologiyalar asosida talabalar mediamentalitetini rivojlantirishda sun'iy intellekt (AI) dasturlaridan foydalanishning tahliliy modeli	140
Rustamova Nodira Rustamovna	
Talabalarda kooperativ ta'lim asosida motivatsiyani rivojlantirish usullari	145
Sitora Toshmatova	
STEAM yondashuvi asosida boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilarida kreativ kompetensiyani shakllantirishning zaruriyati	149
Tashibekova Munajat Xoshimovna	
Musiqqa ta'limining pedagogik asoslari va metodik tizimi	153
Toshpulatova Saida Kuzibaevna	
Texnologiya fanini o'qitishda eng samarali metodlardan foydalanish	158
Turdiyeva Shahzoda Eshdavlrat qizi	
Enhancing University Students' Self-Directed Learning Through Edtech Tools	161
Ulasheva Lobar	
Fanlararo loyiha ishlarini tashkil etish orqali o'quvchilarning dizayn fikrlash salohiyatini oshirish	164
Valiyeva Nargiza Athamboevna	
Alohida ta'lim ehtiyojiga ega o'quvchilarning kasbiy faoliyatga tayyorlashning pedagogik-psixologik asoslari	169
Xakimova Sarvinov Sharifjon qizi	
Sun'iy intellekt asosida yaratilgan ta'lim platformalari: samaradorlik tahlili va pedagogik yondashuvlar	173
Xanbabayev Hakimjon Ikramovich, Erkinov Jasurbek Hasanjon o'g'li	
Tasavvufdagi “muhosaba” va “tafakkur” amallarining o'z-o'zini refleksiya metodlari sifatida qo'llanilishi	176
Xoshimov Nuriddin Mamadaliyevich	
Milliy sport va ommaviy o'yinlarning badiiy-estetik ahamiyati	182
Yaxyayeva Sojida Abdurahimovna	
Ota-ona mehriining bola psixologiyasiga ta'siri	185
Yulchiyeva Shohsanam Dilshod qizi	
Nutq rivojlanishi orqada qolgan bolalarda qo'llaniladigan innovatsion usullari samaradorligi	189
Ahmedova Nargiza Muzaffarovna	
Факторы, сдерживающие развитие науки в контексте требований к диссертационным работам	193
Зайналов Жахонгир Расулович, Нурмухамедов Аббос Мамадалиевич, Шадманов Камолиддин Кажакджанович, Самигова Нодира Хамидуллаевна	
Структура и стратегии развития предметных компетенций	197
Наимова Мафтунабону Файзулложоновна	
Психологическая консультация: современная практика, задачи и перспективы развития	203
Раупова Шохида Ахроровна	
Подготовка будущих педагогов к инклюзивному обучению детей с ограниченными возможностями здоровья: задачи и перспективы	207
Сайфутдинова Насиба Нурматовна	
Формирование иноязычной грамотности у курсантов военных вузов: социально-психологические факторы	211
Сулейманова Нилуфар Камилловна	
O'qituvchi shaxsiy kompetensiyasining mohiyati va pedagogik faoliyatdagi o'rni	214
Abdiraxmonova Guliston Muzaffar qizi	
Bolalarda axloqiy qadriyatlarini shakllantirish jarayonining milliy va umuminsoniy tamoyillari	218
Abdumutalipova Gulshodaxon Nurbek qizi	
Fuqarolik jamiyatida huquqiy madaniyat va uni rivojlantirish jarayonlari	221
Abdusalimova Shaxnoza Quduratullayevna	
Ta'lim menejmenti tizimida o'qituvchining nutq madaniyatini rivojlantirish strategiyalari	224
Abduxalilova Iroda Nozimxonovna	

MUNDARIJA СОДЕРЖАНИЕ CONTENTS

O'zbekistonda yoshlarni ijtimoiy-pedagogik hamkorlikda tarbiyalashda "Uzluksiz ma'naviy tarbiya konsepsiyasi"ning ustuvor vazifalari	229
Abirova Umida Nazarovna	
Bo'lajak boshlang'ich sinf o'qituvchilarini inklyuziv ta'lim sharoitida differensiyalashtirilgan dars mashg'ulotlarini tashkil etishga o'rgatish (kompetentligini shakllantirish/rivojlantirish) usullari.....	232
Adhamova Diyora Sanjar qizi	
Musobaqa faoliyati samaradorligini oshirishda sambochilarning energiya sarfi va tiklanish mexanizmlari tahliliy	239
Tangriyev Abdukarim Tovashevich	
Aksiologik yondashuv asosida bo'lajak jismoniy tarbiya o'qituvchilarining harakat faolligini takomillashtirishning ijtimoiy-pedagogik zaruriyati.....	244
Hafizov Shahriyor Shavkatovich	
Bo'lajak tarbiyachilarning transversal: tanqidiy va innovatsion fikrlash kompetensiyalari	248
Jaloliddinova Maftunaxon Mahmudjon qizi	
Axborotning gnoseologik mohiyati.....	256
Kamolova Munojatxon Jaloldinovna	
Maktabgacha yoshdagi bolalar nutqini rivojlantirish yo'llari	259
Mamatova Aziza Bo'riboevna	
Akademik litseylarda kimyo fanini o'qitishda raqamli ta'lim texnologiyalaridan foydalanish imkoniyatlari....	262
Maxamadiyev Sharofiddin Jumaboyevich	
Pedagogik oliy ta'limda talabalarning kasbiy ijtimoiylashuvini korporativ madaniyat asosida rivojlantirish metodikasi.....	267
Maxkamova Dilafuz Aliyevna	
Bo'lajak o'qituvchilar uchun xorijiy tillarni o'qitishda lingvomadaniy yondashuv	271
Normamatova Kamola Gulmamat qizi	
O'zbek tili izohli lug'atida iboralarning grammatik tavsifi (bosh komponentli iboralar misolida).....	274
S. Sh. Azamatova	
Oila instituti va gender tenglikni ta'minlashning ijtimoiy-huquqiy muammolari	277
Salayeva Aziza Muhammadmurot qizi	
Gender yondashuv asosida talaba-qizlarda tanqidiy fikrlashni rivojlantirishning namunaviy mezonlari.....	282
Xolova Mohigul Shavkatovna	
Pedagogika yo'nalishi talabalari huquqiy savodxonligini rivojlantirish metodlarini takomillashtirish.....	287
Xudoyberganov Atham	
Boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilarida leksik komponentlikni TRIZ texnologiyasi yordamida rivojlantirish	291
Zokirova Sohiba Muxtoraliyevna, Fayzullayeva Nazokat Uchqun qizi	
Цифровизация и трансформация образования как социально-педагогическое явление	295
Кадирова Наргиза Азаматовна	
Методика формирования креативного мышления у студентов-филологов на основе проблемно-ориентированных заданий (на материале английского языка)	298
Мамырбаева Дина	
Структура и стратегии развития предметных компетенций	304
Наимова Мафтунабону Файзулложоновна	
Kichik maktab yoshidagi o'quvchilarda morfologik kompetentlikni shakllantirish	308
Ganiyeva Shodiya Azizovna	
Модель "4+1+1" как ключевой механизм в системе практической подготовки учителей музыки.....	313
Мухитдинова Малохатхон Саиджабборовна	
Tarbiya fanini o'qish samaradorligini oshirishda raqamli texnologiyalardan foydalanish.....	317
Nazarova Nasiba Abdullayevna	
Tarbiyachining kasbiy psixologik xususiyatlari.....	320
Shamshetova Anjim Karamaddinovna	
Boshlang'ich ta'limda tarbiya nazariyasi va metodologiyasi.....	323
Bo'ronova Iroda Bo'ronovna	
Yosh dzyudochi qizlarning mashg'ulotlar jarayonida jismoniy tayyorgarligini oshirish texnologiyalari	327
Matmuratova Iroda Baxtiyor qizi	
"Odob us-solihin" asarida yoritilgan axloqiy-didaktik g'oyalar va uning pedagogik mazmuni.....	332
A. N. Nusratov	
Bo'lajak boshlang'ich sinf o'qituvchilarini kasbiy kompetentligini takomillashtirishning metodik asoslari	336
Xolmatov Pardaboy Qoraboevich, Abdurasulova Dilnoza	

Bo'lajak boshlang'ich sinf o'qituvchilari faoliyatida loyihalashtirishning o'rni	342
<i>Abdusattorova Go'zalxon Abdulxabib qizi</i>	
Tibbiyot va frazeologiya inson omilida	346
<i>Achilov Muzaffar Norquliyevich</i>	
Boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilarida fazoviy tasavvurlarni rivojlantirishda matematikaning ahamiyati	349
<i>Mamasaidova Muhabbat Abdulalom qizi, Akbaraliyeva Marjona Xurshid qizi</i>	
Ekoestetik kompetensiyani shakllantirishning xorijiy va milliy tajribalar tahlili	354
<i>Alijonova Maftuna Maxamadjon qizi</i>	
Pedagogik jarayonda talabalarda qadriyatli munosabatlarni shakllantirish mexanizmlari	359
<i>Alikulova Muxayyo Sherovna</i>	
Ingliz ritsarlik romanlarining lingvopoetik tahlili	362
<i>Durdona Boychayeva, Aliyeva Elmira</i>	
Maktabgacha ta'limda estetik tarbiya berishning pedagogik asoslari	365
<i>Altibayeva Gulbaxor Majitovna</i>	
Kasbiy kompetensiya tushunchasining mazmuni mohiyati va tarkibiy tuzilmasi	369
<i>Axmadjonova Jasmira Jamshid qizi</i>	
Developing Writing Competence Among CEFR B1 and Ielts Learners Experiencing Difficulties in English Language Acquisition	374
<i>Ayturayev Majid Mavlankhanovich</i>	
Ta'lim jarayonida ijtimoiy intellektni rivojlantirishning milliy qadriyatlarga asoslangan modeli	378
<i>Azamov Umarxon Yaxyoxonovich</i>	
Complications in Teaching Argumentative Speech to Students in Grades 8–9	383
<i>Buribayeva Aziza Ismatillaevna</i>	
Interfaol o'yinlar orqali maktabgacha yoshdagi bolalarda ijtimoiy-emotsional ko'nikmalarni shakllantirishning pedagogik asoslari	386
<i>Buriyeva Aziza Nematovna</i>	
Maktabgacha ta'lim tashkilotlarida maktabgacha katta yoshdagi bolalarning ijodiy faolligini shakllantirish	390
<i>Davronova Sevinch</i>	
O'quvchilarda milliy va umummadaniy kompetensiyani rivojlantirishda maqollardan foydalanish bo'yicha manbaalar tahlili	394
<i>Boltayeva Barno, Eliboyeva Surayyo Abdulkarim qizi</i>	
Social Roots and Psychological Consequences of Domestic Violence	399
<i>Dumarova Gulmira Kozimbekovna, Mamadaliyeva Gulmira, Sultonova Zulhayo</i>	
The Transversal-Methodical Competence of a Preschool Educator is the Foundation of Effective And Quality Education	402
<i>Ergasheva Barno Ziyavitdin kizi</i>	
Maktabgacha yoshdagi bolalarga ta'lim-tarbiya berishning innovatsion yo'llari	406
<i>Erkinova Mehriniso Ro'ziboyevna</i>	
Boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilarining o'qish savodxonligini oshirish strategiyalari	411
<i>Eshonkulova Hilola Rajab qizi</i>	
Ta'lim jarayonida o'qituvchi va o'quvchi o'rtasidagi muloqotning bilish faoliyatiga ta'siri	415
<i>Habibova Shyira Baxtiyorovna</i>	
Ruhiy rivojlanishi sustlashgan boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilarida o'qish buzilishlarini aniqlash va bartaraf etish	419
<i>Ikromova Sarvinoz Siroj qizi</i>	
Bo'lajak o'qituvchilarda riskologik kompetentlikni shakllantirishning pedagogik-psixologik xususiyatlari	424
<i>Jabborova Dilafuz Furqatovna</i>	
Maktabgacha yoshdagi bolalarda chet tili o'rganish jarayonida kommunikativ kompetensiyani rivojlantirishning psixologik asoslari	428
<i>Jurayeva Sug'diyona Shamsiddin qizi</i>	
Transforming Education: The Impact of Emerging Technologies on Modern Pedagogical Practices	431
<i>Kadirova Ferangiz Himmatillo qizi</i>	
Salomatlik etikasi konsepsiyasi va pedagogik madaniyat – talabalar ma'naviyati va dunyoqarashini shakllantirishdagi roli	435
<i>Kamalova Yoqutxon Bahodirovna</i>	

Tarbiyachilarning kasbiy mahoratini takomillashtirish va pedagogik faoliyat samaradorligini oshirish omillari	439
Kenjayeva Dildora Terkashevna	
Maktab ta'lim tizimida innovatsiyalarning o'rni va ahamiyati	443
Kistabayeva Gulchexra Djurakulovna	
Kichik maktab yoshi davrida o'quv faoliyati va o'quv motivlarining shakllanishi	448
Latifa Zarifovna Korayeva	
Maktabgacha ta'lim tizimining raqamlashtirilishi: xalqaro tajriba va istiqbollar	451
Mahmudova Zulfiya Homidovna, Hoshimova Dilnoza Boymirzoevna	
Boshlang'ich sinf o'qituvchilarini dizayn tafakkurga o'rgatishda STEAM yondashuvining didaktik imkoniyatlari	454
Mamadaminova Munisa Maxmudjon qizi, Boboxonova Shodiyona Rustam qizi	
Tabiatni asrash – kelajakni asrash: Buxoro misolida	459
Mardonova Saodat Muzaffarovna	
Bo'lajak pedagoglarda o'z-o'zini baholash kompetentligini shakllantirish va rivojlantirish	463
Meyliyeva Nafosat Gulomovna	
Sun'iy intellektning ta'limda kognitiv va metakognitiv jarayonlarga ta'siri	466
Murodov Ulug'bek O'tkir o'g'li	
Maktabgacha ta'limda inklyuziv ta'limning tashkil etilishi	470
Mustofoyeva Muhabbat Husniddin qizi	
The Effectiveness of Art Therapy in Working With Children Experiencing Emotional Stress	473
Nargiza Khayrullayevna Ortikova, Laziz Azizovich Normuratov	
Maktabgacha ta'lim tarbiyalanuvchilarining musiqiy qobiliyatlarini rivojlantirish mexanizmlari	477
Ortiqov Akmaljon Abdusalom o'g'li	
CLIL metodining O'zbekiston ta'lim tizimida qo'llanilishi	481
Qarshiyeva Sarvinoz Ural qizi	
The Use of Mobile Apps to Build Vocabulary Proficiency	486
Kosimov Sunnat Ravshan ugli	
Yoshlar tafakkurini rivojlantirish va ma'naviyatini oshirishda tasviriy san'atning o'rni	490
Quvonchbek Abduxamidov	
Axborot texnologiyalari ta'sirida san'at tushunchasining o'zgarishi	494
Rajabova Laylo O'tkir qizi	
Bo'lajak tarbiyachilarning kasbiy kompetensiyalarini rivojlantirish texnologiyalari	498
Ramozonova Bahoroy Sadriddinovna	
Boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilarining nutqiy kompetensiyalarini shakllantirishda innovatsion yondashuvlarning pedagogik asoslari	501
Yusufzoda Shabnami Yunus, Rashidova Saida Ravshonbek qizi	
Axborot texnologiyalarini fizika darslarida qo'llash	506
Raxmanov Valijon Turdaliyevich, O'razaliyev Alijon Xasan o'g'li	
Axborot xavfsizligini o'qitishda sun'iy intellektdan foydalanish afzalliklari	510
Raxmetova Lazzat	
Eshitishda nuqsonli bo'lgan bolalarning psixologik xususiyatlarining o'ziga xosligi	513
S. A. Mamatisayeva	
Androgogik yondashuvning integrativ metodikasi	517
Sattorova Shaxlo Axadovna	
Gendered Language in Uzbek and English Media Discourse	520
Sultonova Charos Iskandar kizi	
Maktabga tayyorlov yoshdagi bolalarda ijtimoiy ekologik dunyoqarashni shakllantirishga ta'sir qiluvchi omillar	527
Suyunova Matluba Abdusaidovna	
Empatiya shifokor–pasiyent munosabatida: tibbiyot talabalarining psixologik tayyorgarligi	531
Tajiboyeva Odinoxon Rustamjon qizi, Qurbonova Fotima Farhodjon qizi	
Modern Approaches to Teaching Grammar	534
Tuychiyev Azamat Farkhod ugli	
The Importance of Psychological Preparation of Preschool Children for School Education	538
Turamov Muhammadzohid Rustamjon o'g'li	

Bo'lajak maktabgacha ta'lim tashkilotlari tarbiyachi-pedagoglarining kasbiy-axloqiy kompetentligini rivojlantirish	541
<i>Xabibullayeva Sayyoraxon Maxamadali qizi</i>	
Imkoniyati cheklangan va sog'lom bolalar faoliyatida universal ta'limning imkoniyati	544
<i>Xolmatova Sarvinoz Raxmatilla qizi</i>	
Kurashchilarning umumiy va maxsus sport tayyorgarliklari.....	548
<i>Xudoyberganov Javlonbek Soatboy o'g'li</i>	
Tayyorlov guruhi tarbiyalanuvchilarida ekologik kompetentlik tushunchalarini rivojlantirish bosqichlari.....	551
<i>Yarova Gulhayo Fazliddin qizi</i>	
Arxitektura va dizayn yo'nalishi bitiruvchilarini kasbga yo'naltirish vositasida axborot almashish jarayonlarini optimallashtirish metodikasini takomillashtirish.....	555
<i>Kuchimov M. K.</i>	
Yuqori sinf o'quvchilarining ma'naviy kompetentligini jadidlarning pedagogik qarashlari asosida shakllantirish metodikasi (Temurbeklar maktablari misolida)	559
<i>Quldashev Murodjon G'aniyevich</i>	
Лингвистическое исследование влияния социальных сетей на синтаксические изменения в языке современного поколения.....	562
<i>Шавилова Наталья Сергеевна</i>	
Boshlang'ich sinf o'qituvchisining nutq madaniyati.....	566
<i>Islamova Dilfuza Dilshodovna, Gulimbayeva Barno</i>	
Особенности гражданского воспитания обучающихся в системе "школа–маҳалля" в Узбекистане ...	570
<i>Хайдаров Шавкат Шамсиддин угли</i>	
Mantiqiy masalalarni bajarishning metodik usullari	575
<i>Tosheva Yulduz</i>	
Bo'lajak ofitserlarni harbiy-vatanparvarlik ruhida tarbiyalashda pedagogik-psixologik omillar (jamoat xavfsizligini ta'minlash bo'linmalari misolida)	579
<i>Yarmatov Akbar Normurotovich</i>	
Yosh harbiy xizmatchi ofitserlarda muloqot madaniyatini samarali shakllantirish muammosining xorijiy tadqiqotlardagi talqini	582
<i>Matyakubov Elyor Rajapovich</i>	

COMPLICATIONS IN TEACHING ARGUMENTATIVE SPEECH TO STUDENTS IN GRADES 8–9

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Abstract: The article explores the theoretical and methodological foundations of teaching oral argumentative speech to 8th–9th grade students in English classes. It reveals that argumentation is a complex cognitive and communicative process combining linguistic, logical, psychological, and sociocultural components. The author identifies the key difficulties learners encounter in mastering reasoned speech—such as ambiguity of lexical meaning, insufficient logical coherence, lack of argumentative strategies, and limited vocabulary for expressing cause–effect relationships. Drawing on the works of Elukhina (1996), Budden (2007), Mayfield (2014), and Hasibuan et al. (2020), the study classifies the main types of errors in students' argumentative speech and correlates them with linguistic and psychological factors. A comprehensive typology of challenges—linguistic, sociocultural, logical–semantic, and psychological—is proposed, serving as a framework for developing targeted teaching methods. The article concludes that systematic work on critical thinking, lexical enrichment, and argumentation modeling is essential for forming students' argumentative competence at the A2–B1 levels, ensuring effective participation in dialogic and monologic communication.

Key words: argumentation, oral speech, English classes, critical thinking, linguistic competence, cognitive processes, communicative strategies.

Annotatsiya: Maqolada ingliz tili darslarida 8–9-sinf o'quvchilariga og'zaki argumentativ nutqni o'rgatishning nazariy va metodologik asoslari tahlil qilinadi. Unda argumentatsiya til, mantiq, psixologiya va sotsiokulturni o'zida birlashtiruvchi murakkab bilish hamda kommunikativ jarayon sifatida talqin etiladi. Muallif o'quvchilar tomonidan asosli nutqni egallash jarayonida uchraydigan asosiy qiyinchiliklarni aniqlaydi, jumladan: leksik ma'nolarning noaniqligi, mantiqiy izchillikning yetishmasligi, argumentativ strategiyalarning sustligi va sabab–natija munosabatlarini ifodalash uchun so'z boyligining cheklanganligi. Eluxina (1996), Budden (2007), Meyfield (2014) va Hasibuan va boshqalarning (2020) ishlariga tayanilgan holda, maqolada o'quvchilarning argumentativ nutqidagi xatolar turlari til va psixologik omillar bilan bog'liq holda tasniflanadi. Tahlil asosida tilshunoslik, sotsiokulturniy, mantiqiy–semantik va psixologik jihatlardan iborat muammolar tipologiyasi ishlab chiqilgan. Maqola xulosasiga ko'ra, tanqidiy fikrlashni rivojlantirish, lug'at boyligini kengaytirish va argumentatsiya modellarini tizimli qo'llash o'quvchilarda A2–B1 darajadagi argumentativ kompetensiyani shakllantirishning muhim sharti hisoblanadi.

Kalit so'zlar: argumentativ nutq, og'zaki nutq, ingliz tili darslari, tanqidiy fikrlash, lingvistik kompetensiya, kognitiv jarayonlar, kommunikativ strategiyalar.

Аннотация: В статье рассматриваются теоретические и методические основы обучения устной аргументативной речи учащихся 8–9-х классов на уроках английского языка. Аргументация определяется как сложный когнитивный и коммуникативный процесс, объединяющий языковые, логические, психологические и социокультурные компоненты. Автор выявляет основные трудности, с которыми сталкиваются учащиеся при овладении аргументированной речью: неоднозначность лексического значения, недостаточная логическая связность, ограниченность аргументативных стратегий и недостаточный словарный запас для выражения причинно–следственных связей. Опираясь на работы Элухиной (1996), Бадден (2007), Мэйфилда (2014) и Хасибуана и др. (2020), исследование классифицирует типы ошибок в аргументативной речи учащихся и соотносит их с лингвистическими и психологическими факторами. Предложена комплексная типология трудностей – лингвистических, социокультурных, логико–семантических и психологических, – служащая основой для разработки целенаправленных методов обучения. В заключение подчеркивается, что системная работа над критическим мышлением, расширением словарного запаса и моделированием аргументации является необходимым условием формирования аргументативной компетенции учащихся на уровнях А2–В1 и обеспечивает их эффективное участие в диалогическом и монологическом общении.

Ключевые слова: аргументация, устная речь, уроки английского языка, критическое мышление, лингвистическая компетенция, когнитивные процессы, коммуникативные стратегии.

INTRODUCTION

In the course of this study, it was revealed that argumentation is an integral part of both dialogical and monological forms of speech. In general, argumentation is a complex speech act aimed at establishing one's opinion through evidence or justification, as evidenced by everything described earlier. Therefore, let's turn to the difficulties in learning reasoned speech. It has been repeatedly emphasized in the methodological literature that teaching both dialogical and monologic speech in English is difficult linguistically and psycholinguistically, especially when it comes to argumentation.

LITERATURE REVIEW

At first glance, it seems that learning monologic speech is more difficult, since it requires logical consistency in the development of thoughts – in the use of logical and semantic connections, etc. However, any dialogue also requires this, especially since dialogic and monologic speech always overlap. For example, when describing a picture, the teacher can ask leading questions, or during the dialogue, a monologue can be used – a description of some things, actions, etc. In the course of oral communication, according to N. V. Elukhina (1996, p. 51), difficulties arise related to:

- the linguistic form of the message;
- the semantic content of the message;
- the conditions for presenting information;
- the sources of information.

Applying this classification to the teaching of reasoned types of speech, we can say that reasoned speech is multi-component and requires mastery of speech patterns and various techniques (strategies) of argumentation, persuasion, and agreement. The second and third difficulties, in our opinion, are directly related to the lack of formation of the skills of understanding speech or decoding meanings both during dialogue and monologue. In turn, the fourth difficulty may come from presenting unfamiliar information and the complexity of the text itself. However, the main difficulty in the field of oral reasoned speech is the process of argumentation itself in the logic of the organization of cause-and-effect relationships, which are sometimes formulated not always relevant to the logical nature of the act of argumentation, which causes misunderstanding in the interlocutor or misleads him, distorting intentions or thoughts [Budden 2007; Mayfield 2014; Hasibuan et al. 2020].

It is in this regard that the greatest number of errors in students' speech is observed, as evidenced by the results of the analysis of written argumentative rhetoric and the classification of errors presented in the book by M. Mayfield (2014). A similar classification of errors regarding oral reasoned speech is described in other studies [Hasibuan et al. 2020].

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Taking into account the proposed classifications of logical errors and personal experience in school, as well as observing the speech of both teachers and students regarding reasoned speech, it is possible to systematize errors in reasoned speech as follows: ambiguity and inaccuracy of the words used, which lead to loss of certainty and precision; the lexico-semantic saturation of the means of expressing thoughts and the bias of judgments do not allow recognizing the true meaning of the speaker's intention and correctness; simplification of sentences and avoidance of two-part sentences, so the elements of argumentation may blur; assertiveness and pressure on the partner to be right cause the communication partner to develop a psychological barrier to defending his point of view or formulating a counterargument; excessive reliance on a factual source sometimes leads to confusion of the communication partner, since the communication partner may have other sources of truth that prove correctness; the use of contradictory ideas, which confuses the interlocutor; and the use of similar examples, which does not always give a positive result in terms of logical and semantic argumentation.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

In many ways, this list of errors or inaccuracies in oral reasoned speech correlates with the results of a study of the elements of argumentation and logical fallacies of Indonesian students in the work of S. H. Hasibuan, I. D. Manurung, and Yu. Yustriati (2020). As has been mentioned more than once, argumentation arises to make their statements convincing and reasonable, and to identify similar positions or inconsistencies in the views of the communicants, as a result of which the interlocutors must come to a compromise or a joint agreement. In accordance with this, the following classification of arguments is considered to be the most common

in structural terms: simple forms in the form of a single premise statement; composite arguments reflecting alternative points of view; a coordinating set of arguments consisting of a combination or set of arguments, explanations, evidence, and conclusions; and a subordinate set of arguments, which is a multi-layered set of arguments derived from one another [Eemeren et al. 2002; Hasibuan et al. 2020]. One way or another, the first three structural types can be used by students in grades 8–9 during the formulation of reasoned speech, and the fourth is the most complex and therefore its implementation is possible at subsequent stages of schooling. In our opinion, the work of researchers S. H. Hasibuan, I. D. Manurung, and Yu. Yustriati (2020) is valuable for understanding which types are most preferred in student voting and their percentage activity. So, the object of analysis and control was a student discussion set on a specific problem, which was recorded on a dictaphone and then reformatted into a written text. After that, the recorded discussion was analyzed in the context of the use of argumentation elements and the presence of logical errors. It is significant that all the above-mentioned types of arguments (simple, multi-part, coordinate, and subordinate) were used by students but in different percentages. The fourth type of argument turned out to be the least used in comparison with other types, which confirms our idea of the complexity and multi-component nature of this type of argument even for students. According to the results of the discussion analysis, it was revealed that the recorded mistakes of students were mainly caused by difficulties associated with the logical, mental, and psychological features of reasoned speech, as well as errors in the forms of linguistic expression of argumentation of the coordinate and subordinate types. At the same time, scientists conclude that an expanded vocabulary is needed to more accurately express the elements of argumentation in the second and third types [Hasibuan et al. 2020].

CONCLUSION AND SUGGESTIONS

We agree with this conclusion, but we must also take into account that the main difficulty lies in the fact that argumentation, as a complex speech act, involves reasoning in internal speech and reflection related to critical thinking when formulating thoughts in internal and external speech. All this requires special work on the formation and development of critical thinking and lexico-grammatical skills based on speech models widely used in the course of reasoned speech. Nevertheless, it is also necessary to take into account the language level of the contingent of subjects in the analyzed study, where there were university students, and they already have sufficiently formed critical thinking and possess a certain lexical and grammatical stock. And if the subjects of learning are schoolchildren in grades 8–9, then, naturally, the level, as well as the qualitative and quantitative sides of reasoned speech, should be at the A2 level and less simplified both in linguistic and logical terms of reasoning, in particular, in the three types of argumentation.

List of References:

1. Budden, J. (2007). *Teaching English: Developing Speaking Skills*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
2. Eemeren, F. H. van, Grootendorst, R., & Henkemans, F. S. (2002). *Argumentation: Analysis, Evaluation, Presentation*. Mahwah, NJ: Lawrence Erlbaum Associates.
3. Elizarova, G. V. (2005). *Culture and Communication: Teaching Cross-Cultural Communication in Foreign Language Lessons*. St. Petersburg: KARO.
4. Elukhina, N. V. (1996). *Listening and Speaking in the Process of Communication: Psychological and Methodological Aspects*. Moscow: Vysshaya Shkola.
5. Hasibuan, S. H., Manurung, I. D., & Yustriati, Y. (2020). An analysis of argumentation elements and logical fallacies in students' discussions. *Journal of English Language Teaching and Linguistics*, 5(1), 45–58.

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- 13.00.00 Pedagogika fanlari
 - 13.00.01 Pedagogika nazariyasi. Pedagogik ta'limotlar tarixi
 - 13.00.02 Ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi (sohalar bo'yicha)
 - 13.00.03 Maxsus pedagogika
 - 13.00.04 Jismoniy tarbiya va sport mashg'ulotlari nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.05 Kasb-hunar ta'limi nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.06 Elektron ta'lim nazariyasi va metodikasi (ta'lim sohaları va bosqichlari bo'yicha)
 - 13.00.07 Ta'limda menejment
 - 13.00.08 Maktabgacha ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.09 Ijtimoiy pedagogika
 - 07.00.00 Tarix fanlari
 - 19.00.00 Psixologiya fanlari
 - 01.00.00 Fizika-matematika fanlari
 - 02.00.00 Kimyo fanlari
 - 03.00.00 Biologiya fanlari
 - 09.00.00 Falsafa fanlari
 - 10.00.00 Filologiya fanlari
 - 11.00.00 Geografiya fanlari

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